

Pollen sampler construction guide with pictures

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1. Drill the hole right in the center of the bottom of the bigger part of the project box. ($1/16$ " drill bit or similar)

2. Drill the hole in the center of the bottom of the motor holder, using the same drill bit. (1 1/64" drill bit or similar)

3. Drill the holes for mounting screws, placing one of them in the middle axis of the box.
4. Insert and tighten all 3 screws and add nuts inside of the project box. Note: it may be useful to put the screw on one side upside down with the nut on the motor holder side to give more flexibility about battery holder and pcb placement inside the project box.

This screw can optionally be installed in the other direction with the nut on the outside of the box

5. Drill a hole in the side of the box using $\frac{3}{4}$ " drill.

6. Place the switch inside of the hole with cables to inside. Mount it with a hot glue if needed.

7. Solder the top six pins to microcontroller, longer side up.

8. It is now possible to upload program to microcontroller right now, connecting pins to computer through FTDI cable.

- Download the Arduino IDE: <https://www.arduino.cc/en/software>
- Open the sampling script (included in this repository) and customize the sampling script as desired
- Attach the FTDI cable; make sure that the cable orientation matches the pin descriptions (“BLK” connects to the black wire on the FTDI cable and “GRN” connects to the green wire, although descriptions may vary among different Arduino Pro Mini boards)
- Update the settings to match the board under the “Tools” menu:
 - For “Board” select the “Arduino Pro or Pro Mini” option
 - For processor select “Atmega 328P (5V, 16 MHz)”
 - For port, select the USB port that the FTDI cable is plugged into. Depending on the computer, this may take a little effort
- Press “Upload” (under the “Sketch” menu or the right facing green arrow at the top of the page)

9. Solder female pins to PCB board. Only GND, VCC and pin 13 necessary to solder. Including these female pins will allow you to easily remove and replace the Arduino Pro Mini if it is damaged.

10. Solder male pins to the bottom of the microcontroller.
11. Plug it into female pins on PCB.

12. Solder diode into PCB. Cut protruding pins from the bottom. Make sure that the diode is placed with the silver line to the right (i.e., on the side of JP3, not JP4; an earlier version of the board had the orientation of the diode misprinted).

13. Solder the Mosfet transistor to PCB. Cut protruding pins from the bottom.

14. Solder bent pins to voltage regulator.

15. It is now necessary to use the built in potentiometer on the voltage regulator to the voltage required to turn the motor at the desired speed. With this design, that voltage is 6.0 V, which will result in a rotation rate of 2400 RPM of the sampling head. You can adjust the voltage of the regulator using a small screw driver. To begin, set the voltage to the minimum value by turning the potentiometer counter clockwise until it can not be easily turned. Note that the potentiometer is fragile, so be very gentle with it. Details on this regulator and adjusting it are available here: <https://www.pololu.com/product/2118>
16. Create a circuit that will allow you to measure output voltage with a multimeter and connect the regulator to it. This may be most easily done with a breadboard.
17. Gradually increase voltage on regulator to 5.95-6.05 V.
18. Remove the regulator from the testing circuit

19. Solder the adjusted regulator into PCB.

20. Solder wires to motor.

21. Place the motor in holder. Pull the cables through the hole in the box and trim wires to a convenient length. (note: the wire colors that come with this particular switch may lead to some confusion; other switches without attached wires can be purchased but using them requires slightly more soldering).

22. Connect “+” cable from battery holder with black cable (“on” side) from the switch (solder and then add electrical tape).

23. Solder black cable from battery holder to GND on PCB.

24. Solder red wire from the switch (“off” side) with VIN on the PCB.

25. Solder the red “+” wire from the motor to JP3 on PCB and black “-” wire to JP4.

Note: the motor and battery wires in this example were not trimmed before connecting them so there will be more wire in this sampler than necessary

26. Mount motor in holder using hot glue. Make sure the motor is approximately level. Now you can turn on the switch to see if circuit works. Note: to easily remove hot glue, use rubbing alcohol and a cotton swab. At this point, you can also mount the pcb in the project box using a dab of hot glue at the corners or some other adhesive. The motor can be mounted with a screw.

27. Close the box.

28. Take 3D-printed head and take out moving parts. Use knife for Styrofoam cutting if needed.
29. Gently sand off any unevenness remaining after 3D printing and put parts back together.

CONVERSIONS

inches \times 25.4 = millimeters feet \times 0.3048 = meters
inches \times 2.54 = centimeters yards \times 0.9144 = meters
miles \times 1.609344 = kilometers

MAYES BROTHERS TOOL MFG. CO

240 250 260 270 280 290 300mm 310 320 330 340 350 360 370 380 390 400mm 410 420 430 440 450 460 470 480 490 500mm

30. Use a tapping bit to create threads in the side hole of the head; this will help with the installation of the set screw

31. Place a piece of thin wire in the holes of the moving parts and make a small loop of it.

32. Repeat it with holes on sides of the head and connect the loops on each side with a spring.

33. Cut two acrylic rods – 1 1/8” length. Depending on the cutting method, it may be advisable to wear safety glasses while cutting rods. These sampling rods will be used for sampling pollen and should be cut in as close to sterile of an environment as possible.

34. Place cut rods in the holes of the sampler head. Note: we have found that this design does not require set screws to hold the rods in place, but set screws can be used if necessary.

35. Apply a little bit of the reflective tape on the side of head.
36. Mount the sampling head on the motor using set screw.

37. Turn on the device and measure RPM using digital tachometer pointed into reflective tape. Follow instructions on the tachometer for how far it should be placed from the sampler. Make sure there are no reflective or bright surfaces behind the sampler head when testing RPM.

Optional rotorod mounting and deployment system

Attach the lid of the project box to the inside of the bucket lid

- To do so, use a few drops of hot glue to secure the lid of the project box to the center of the bucket lid during the installation process
- Drill a hole in center of bucket lid and project box lid and attach eye bolt (shown on left) through both, including nuts on both sides
- Drill two holes in bucket lid corresponding with the holes in two opposite corners of project box lid. To do so easily, drill from the side with the project box lid
- Insert screws (either the screws that come with the project box or machine screws that are ~1 inch/ 25mm long x 0.107 inch/2.7 mm wide) through top of lid, including washers on top of lid.
 - If using machine screws, use a tapping device to thread the plastic of the project box support columns

Attach hanging system to lid

- Cut ~ 10 inches (25cm) of coated wire
- Attach one end of wire to top of tripod
 - This is ideally done by making a small hole in the top of the tripod with a metal punch or drill. An inferior alternate approach is to loop wire around the top of the tripod and tie it in place.
- Tie a carabineer to the bottom of the wire. The total length of wire should be ~ 8 inches (20 cm); cut any extra wire. This carabiner will allow the bucket to easily be attached and detached to the tripod

Using the tripod and bucket mounting system

- Place samplers in buckets to allow for easy transportation to deployment locations while substantially reducing risk of contamination
- To quickly remove the sampler from the bucket lid for battery replacement, consider using an electric drill instead of a handheld screwdriver
- If conditions are windy, the bottom of the tripod legs may be pushed slightly into the ground

Additional photos of sample
preparation and mounting

Preparing for sampling

Cut two pieces of the 3.2 mm (1/8") acrylic rods listed in the bill of materials, each to 28 mm (1 1/8") length with wire cutters, shears, or a similar device. It is advised to wear safety glasses while cutting rods. These sampling rods will be used for sampling pollen and should be prepared in as close to sterile of an environment as possible.

- It is useful to apply a label (e.g., a dot of nail polish) to indicate which surface of the rod is being used for sampling. It may also be useful to designate the final 5 mm of the rod as an area to handle the rod and to exclude that area from analysis.

- To prepare rods, put on a sterile glove and use your finger to apply a thin layer of pure silicone grease (e.g., Trident Silicone Lube) to one side of the acrylic sampling rod. This layer should cover the rod as thinly and evenly as possible; to do so rub your finger back and forth three times. A thin sheen should be visible on the rod.

- Place cut rods in the holes of the sampler head with the sampling side facing the direction the motor spins in (counter-clockwise). Note: we have found that this design does not require set screws to hold the rods in place but set screws can be used if necessary. If not using set screws, it may be advisable to wear safety glasses when operating the device.

Deployment

Pollen identification

- Mount both rods on a microscope slide by placing rods on top of the slide with the sampling surface facing upwards and dribbling hot glue on the ends of each rod to secure them without having any adhesive between the rods and the slide (this could prevent them from being level).

- Place 2 μL of the Calberla solution on the top of each rod using a small dropper or pipette, ideally in two or three smaller drops along the length of the area to be examined. Do not put more Calberla solution on than is required; it should not spill out on either side of the rod.

- Gently place a microscope coverslip across rods and wait at least 5 minutes for pollen grains to rehydrate. For subsequent slides, this step can be done part way through analyzing the last rod of the previous slide.

- Conduct transects as desired to count and identify pollen grains